

Mapping relations in Strabo's *Geography*

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INTRODUCTION

- This study explores a new methodology for understanding ancient spatial thinking
- Building on the **Spatial Turn**, it investigates spatial **relationality** in ancient literary texts
- As a major source for ancient geographical writing, **Strabo's *Geography*** serves as the test-subject
- Hypothesis: mapping semantic relationships between places through networks will give much deeper insight into the full complexity of an ancient literary geography than any 2D cartographic could

METHOD

- Standardizing relationship- and place-types
- **Digital geo-annotation** of Strabo's text in Recogito
- **Network visualizations**
- Analysing the graphs with the aid of **network theory**
- 3 case studies: Sicily, Northeastern Europe, Paphlagonia and Pontus

Figure 1: example of the annotation process using the Recogito software: text- and relationship-tagging.

RESULTS

- Overview of geo-referenced places (see Figure 2)
- Network graphs for each of the 5 relationship-types
- Example of network analysis: Figure 3 shows constellation-patterning around Rome and Pontus, the two competitors of the Mithridatic Wars. But there is only a weak direct link between the two, with most connections going through the nodes of major cities in Pontus. Strabo highlights transformative actions of both powers in these places, resulting in the war being situated mostly geographically rather than historically.

Figure 2: Spread of geo-referenced places in Strabo's chapter on Pontus, generated through Recogito's 'map-view'.

Figure 3: Network graph for 'transformative' relationships in Strabo's chapter on Pontus.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

- **On the methodology:** It offers a valuable addition to traditional 2D visualisations to explore spatial descriptions. The networks function as "deep maps", allowing for more advanced investigation including: topographical and historical/political anchoring of the geography, clusters and strong network links.
- **On Strabo:** Confirms theories on Strabo's writing: Networks suggest a coherent picture of the world, fit within a universal Roman context. But at the same time, the influence of Greek scholarly tradition is clear.
- **Future research:** Method holds much potential for investigating spatial information, as it can be applied to any author, genre or corpus concerned with written geographical data.

Suggested resources

- Barker, E., K. Konstantinidou, B. Kiesling and A. Foka. 2023. 'Journeying through Space and Time with Pausanias's Descriptions of Greece', *Literary Geographies* 9 (1), 124-160.
- Barker, E., S. Bouzarovski, C. Pelling and L. Isaksen (eds). 2016. *New Worlds from Old Texts*, Oxford.
- Dueck, D. 2010. 'The geographical narrative of Strabo of Amasia', in: K.A. Raaflaub and R.J.A. Talbert (eds), *Geography and ethnography. Perceptions of the world in Pre-Modern societies*, Chichester, 236-251.
- Warf, B and S. Arias (eds). 2008. *The Spatial Turn: Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, Oxford.

To see the complete collection of networks and continue the conversation, scan the QR code!

